

Is the Measurement Theory consistent with Quantum Theory?

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Abstract

The act of measurement on a quantum object is only described by an indeterministic evolution to a single eigenstate given by a probability relation. The quantum measurement problem holds that it is necessary to explain why there exist two ways in which the state of the quantum object evolves if and if not a measurement has been performed. The Copenhagen interpretation attempts to solve this problem through an epistemological reasoning for the inevitability of using a macroscopic measuring instrument whose exact state is in principle impossible to determine. The hidden variable interpretation on the other hand uses hidden variables to describe a practically indeterministic violent fluctuation arising from an underlying deterministic description to solve the problem. While similar, these solutions have different interpretations of the uncertainty principle and talk about different types of indeterminacy.

1 Introduction

The measurement problem in quantum mechanics has solidified its position as an obstacle to the consistency of quantum theory. The problem can effectively be described as arising from two seemingly contradicting facts: (1) The wave function describing a quantum object evolves deterministically in accordance with the time dependent Schroedinger equation as a linear superposition of states, in the quantum formalism² and (2) The idea that on performing a measurement on the quantum object, the wave function “collapses” to a single state described by a probability relation independent of the Schroedinger equation, is consistent with empirical data². Any coherent theory of quantum mechanics requires that it addresses this problem and resolves it in order to preserve the consistency of the theory. In this paper I will discuss two different solutions to the measurement problem, starting with a solution in the spirit of the Copenhagen attitude² which focuses on the inevitability of using classical

concepts to describe quantum phenomena, followed by the solution of an alternate interpretation of quantum theory in terms of “hidden” variables^{3;4} which focuses on preserving a strictly causal relationship between the dynamical variables describing a quantum system and its behaviour over time using additional parameters called hidden variables. It is done as an attempt to analyse how these conflicting philosophical attitudes resolve the problem, which is essential for a proper understanding of quantum theory. Unless one were to claim that the formalism of quantum mechanics which has been very successful is wrong, it is clear that the act of measurement has influenced the evolution of the state. However, the answer to how exactly the measurement has influenced the quantum object is quite ambiguous since the exact influence has not been observed. This ambiguity has given rise to different interpretations of quantum mechanics, the most widely held one being the Copenhagen interpretation which represents the philosophical attitude of Neils Bohr and Werner Heisenberg. I will start by introducing the problem in more detail in the following section and then continue to examine the aforementioned solutions in sections 3 and 4. Finally, I will discuss both the solutions in a combined section 5 and talk about some of their limitations.

2 The Quantum Measurement Problem

In order to understand the measurement problem it is important to keep in mind the two ways in which the state of the quantum object evolves: (1) The wave function describing a quantum object evolves deterministically in accordance with the time dependent Schroedinger equation $i\partial_t |\psi\rangle = H |\psi\rangle$ as a linear superposition of states $\psi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c_n |e_n\rangle$, in the quantum formalism¹ and (2) On performing a measurement on the quantum object, the wave function “collapses” to a single state described by a probability relation independent of the Schroedinger equation, in accordance with empirical data. In this case if one performs a measurement of the quantity described by an operator Q at the time t , the state “collapses” immediately to an eigenstate $|e_n\rangle$ with a probability given by the squared inner product between the state immediately before the interaction with the measurement instrument and the eigenstate $|\langle e_n | \psi(t) \rangle|^2$ ^{1;2}. In addition to these two postulates of quantum theory, a third postulate, the composition rule states that two systems described by two wave functions $|\phi\rangle$ and $|\chi\rangle$ within two different Hilbert spaces can be combined into a single system which is described by the tensor product of the two wavefunctions $|\phi\rangle \otimes |\chi\rangle$ ². The tensor product describing the combined system will then also evolve deterministically in accordance with the time dependent Schroedinger equation as a linear superposition of states. As argued by Kober, if nature is to be described by quantum theory, the measuring instrument should also be described by quantum theory which means that it has to be treated as a quantum system. Then, given the three postulates, the following argumentation has been made²:

One should be able to combine the system of the measured object S_1 described by the state $|\psi(t)\rangle$ and that of the measurement instrument S_M

described by the state $|\Psi(t)\rangle$ into a single system S_C described by the tensor product of the two states $|\Psi(t)\rangle \otimes |\psi(t)\rangle$ using the composition rule. If so, the tensor product describing S_C should also evolve deterministically in accordance with the time dependent Schroedinger equation $i\partial t(|\Psi(t)\rangle \otimes |\psi(t)\rangle) = H_C(|\Psi(t)\rangle \otimes |\psi(t)\rangle)$ where H_C is the combined Hamiltonian describing S_C obtained by the addition of the Hamiltonian of the measured system H_ψ , the Hamiltonian of the measurement instrument H_Ψ and an interaction Hamiltonian H_I , $H_C = H_\psi + H_\Psi + H_I^2$. This would mean that in the first case, according to the second postulate, we have an indeterministic, probabilistic description of the system S_C consisting of S_1 and S_M , whereas in the second case discussed above, we have a deterministic description of the “same situation” or S_C . Thus Kober argues that quantum theory contradicts itself.

It is important to note that when it is said the state of the combined system evolves deterministically, it only means that the state evolves according to the deterministic Schroedinger equation. The state or the wavefunction still only helps us to compute the probability density of the position of the measured quantum object. In this way we are still limited by a probabilistic description of nature. The above argumentation attempts to show how the two ways in which the state of a quantum object evolves leads to a contradiction in the context of a quantum system S_1 measured with a measuring instrument S_M , which together form a combined system S_C . The contradiction is that the same situation or S_C is shown to have an indeterministic description in the first case and a deterministic description in the second case. However, in the first case S_C is different from the S_C in the second case in the sense that in the first case, the measurement indeterministically gives us an eigenstate that describes S_1 and is independent of S_M whereas in the second case, we have the state of the combined system that is dependent on the states of both S_1 and S_M that evolves deterministically. Therefore it is the state of S_1 that evolves indeterministically and not that of S_C . If so, what does the measurement in the second case have to say about the state of S_1 and is it at all possible that what S_M in the combined system S_C in the second case has to say about S_1 is similar to the first case? In any case it is seen that the contradiction in the above argumentation isn't as clear as it appears to be. Even so, it is still necessary to explain why there exist two ways in which the state of the quantum object evolves if and if not a measurement has been performed. The most obvious answer to this question is to blame the measurement. This approach is seen in both the solutions which are going to be discussed in this paper. In such a case it becomes important to explain how the evolution has come about through the influence of the measurement, which will be discussed in the following sections of the paper.

3 The Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Theory

“The core of the Copenhagen interpretation is founded in Bohr’s statement that all phenomena which can appear in human experience, no matter if they are everyday phenomena or if they refer to the atomic or subatomic range, have to be described by classical concepts.”² The Copenhagen interpretation is centered around this limitation that restricts any description of nature that we as human beings can come up with to classical descriptions. The reason for this assertion is an epistemological one that states that any and all human perception is inevitably limited to classical thought, as the very preconditions to human experience structure the mind in such a way that classical concepts are in accordance with the concepts of our mind². However, the correspondence between classical concepts and the concepts of our mind does not translate to the correspondence of classical concepts and the actual behaviour of nature on a fundamental level. It is seen that these concepts do not work in quantum theory which can only be described according to our mind’s relation to nature, Kober’s quote on this matter seems to be quite illuminative: “Classical concepts are not suitable to describe the phenomena. But by using several concepts which contradict each other within the realm of our classical thinking we can obtain an understanding of the reality behind these concepts which are only able to yield an idea of this greater reality which is represented inadequately by using them.”² If we were to make any models describing quantum phenomena, we would inevitably have to use classical concepts and this would lead to inadequate and far from real descriptions of nature but even so, such a description would be the closest representation of nature that we as humans can achieve within the structures of our human mind. At the same time these classical concepts are limited by the uncertainty relations². The uncertainty relations have an ontological status which is to say that they are independent of human perception and have completely to do with impossibility of measuring simultaneously position and momentum inherent in nature. This has to do with the absence of states where an exact position and momentum has been defined at the same time. Now coming back to the measurement problem, how does the Copenhagen interpretation attempt to solve the measurement problem? The interpretation itself is ambiguous about how the measurement influences the observed object. It only talks about “something” in the act of measurement that causes a “collapse” of the wave function. The solution discussed in this section of the paper is a solution in the “spirit” of the Copenhagen interpretation proposed by Kober and not a solution that was explicitly proposed with the interpretation in its original form itself. To understand the solution, it is important to remember the core of the Copenhagen interpretation: “All phenomena which can appear in human experience, no matter if they are everyday phenomena or if they refer to the atomic or subatomic range, have to be described by classical concepts.”, therefore experiments also have to be described by classical concepts as well. Then, the following argumentation has been made by Kober²: Since experiments have to

be described by classical concepts, which is to say that a macroscopic measuring instrument has to be used to perform the measurement, the number of particles that this instrument consists of has to be large enough that knowledge of each and every particle's state and entanglement becomes impossible, thus making it impossible to know exactly the state of the measuring instrument. Without this knowledge, it becomes impossible to describe the evolution of the state of the measured system as it will be sensitive to the small changes in the states of the particles that the measuring instrument is made of. Therefore we are only able to describe the evolution of the state using the probability relation.

It has also been suggested that the "collapse" to the single eigenstate is a result of some sort of destruction in the phase relations caused by the interaction with the measuring instrument².

The core of this argument is the inevitability of using the macroscopic system in principle to measure the quantum object and as a consequence the inevitability of the lack of knowledge of the exact state of the measuring instrument. Thus, due to the lack of knowledge as a result of this principle reason, there is the possibility that the second postulate could be derived from the first postulate through such an interaction, which hasn't been described clearly enough and also cannot be described clearly due to the inherent limitation of the human mind. In this case the uncertainty relation is not the reason for the indeterminacy but is an extra limitation on the measurement. It is important to note that all these considerations of the Copenhagen interpretation have been made while keeping in mind a big assumption: "the wave function completely specifies the physical state of an individual system which only gives the probabilities of obtainable results from similar experiments"³. The solution that will be discussed in the next section starts with a disagreement to this assumption and to the idea that this indeterministic description does not arise from an underlying deterministic evolution.

4 A Hidden Variable Theory interpretation of quantum mechanics

The Copenhagen theory makes an assumption that has been subject to the criticism of many: "the wave function completely specifies the physical state of an individual system"³. This assumption has even been criticized by Einstein who strictly believed that there existed a completely deterministic relationship between the "pre-defined" dynamical variables describing the system and the changes in its behaviour over time. His criticism of this assumption is shown in the EPR paper⁵ where he uses the property of the wavefunction to arrive at the conclusion that quantum theory is incomplete. Another notable criticism of this assumption is seen in Bohm's paper suggesting a "hidden variable" interpretation of quantum theory, in order to show that an alternate interpretation where a completely deterministic relationship between the "pre-defined" dynamical variables describing the system and the changes in its behaviour over time is in

fact conceivable. In this interpretation the empirically confirmed probabilistic relations are also treated only as a practical consequence and not as an inherent lack of determinism in quantum phenomena⁴. This alternate interpretation also has its own solution to the measurement problem which will briefly be discussed in this section. For the purposes of this paper it is enough to know that hidden variables are additional elements or parameters permitting a detailed causal and continuous description of all processes³. This particular solution to the measurement problem also resolves the problem by deriving the second postulate from the first one. It uses the additional parameter or the hidden variable to show how the interaction between the measuring instrument and the measured system while evolving deterministically and according to definite laws involves very violent fluctuations that are unpredictable and uncontrollable⁴. All that we are able to predict then is the probability relation $|\langle e_n | \psi(t) \rangle|^2$. In this way we once again obtain the second postulate describing the evolution of a state on measurement. In this case the uncertainty principle is also obtained as a practical limitation on the precision arising from those unpredictable and uncontrollable disturbances caused by the measurement⁴. Two non-commuting operators such as that of position and momentum cannot be measured simultaneously as the measurement of one of the quantities associated with the operator disturbs the system in such a way that it is not possible to measure the other quantity.

5 The differences between the two solutions

The two solutions to the measurement problem that were discussed in the paper are quite similar in their approach despite being based on very different philosophical attitudes. Both of them have to do with some lack of control and predictability or indeterminacy on performing the measurement which they use in order to explain how they derive the second postulate. This kind of similarity is expected because the hidden variable interpretation of Bohm^{3:4} was meant to arrive at similar results to that of the Copenhagen interpretation but with different assumptions and philosophical attitudes. Thus, it becomes important to discuss the exact differences between the two solutions which will be the main focus of this section. A very important difference between the two solutions is the differing status of the uncertainty principle. In Kober's solution² the uncertainty principle is an inherent limitation on the precision with which one can correctly measure simultaneously the momentum and position, whereas in Bohm's solution⁴, the uncertainty principle is a practical limitation on the precision with which the two quantities can simultaneously be measured arising from the disturbance caused by the measurement. Another important difference is the kind of indeterminacy involved in both solutions: 1) In the case of the Bohm solution the indeterminacy is an epistemological one but having a practical reason: the complexity of the interaction makes it impossible to determine the dynamics of the system. In principle such a system could be described deterministically. 2) In the case of the Martin Kober solution the indeterminacy

is also an epistemological one but having a principle reason: It is in principle impossible to describe such a system deterministically due to the limitation of human perception which is our necessity for using classical concepts which according to the interpretation is not in accordance with quantum theory. The other differences in the solutions have mainly to do with the initial assumptions and philosophical attitudes which have been discussed earlier. It might also be useful to talk about the status of completeness of quantum theory in both interpretations. While the Copenhagen interpretation believes that quantum theory is complete, the hidden variable interpretation is of the belief that the theory is incomplete and will continue to be so until the discovery of hidden variables³. It is also important to know that despite the considerable consistency of both the interpretations, they also have some limitations. To start with, the Copenhagen interpretation is not adequate in the domain of distances less than $10^{-13}cm^3$. Also as you can see in section 3, Martin Kober's solution isn't provable nor disprovable. Much of the Copenhagen interpretation is also of the same nature and is in principle unverifiable if true. As for the hidden variable interpretation, such hidden variables have as of yet not been discovered experimentally³ and as such, there is no reason to believe that this interpretation is more true than the other considering that both the interpretations are very consistent.

6 Summary and Conclusion

In this paper, it has been discussed the quantum measurement problem, the resolution of which is very important to the consistency of quantum theory. It has been seen that some of the contradictions that arise from this problem are not as clear as they appear to be. It has also been discussed the Copenhagen and a particular hidden variable interpretation of quantum theory and their solutions to the measurement problem, which are similar despite their conflicting philosophical attitudes. Very clear differences between the two solutions have also been pointed out however, especially regarding the interpretation of the uncertainty principle and the type of indeterminacy in the solutions. Only two of the many solutions to the measurement problem have been discussed in this paper. For a deeper understanding of the measurement problem, one must examine and compare the other interpretations of the theory and their solutions to the problem, a few notable ones being Hugh Everett's many-worlds interpretation, the pilot wave interpretation and the Ghirardi-Rimini-Weber theory. Doing so might also be important when synthesizing a new interpretation of quantum theory.

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